

Metal-nano ceramics and its characterizations in rubber like material.

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Abstract:

The needed molar ratio of copper nitrate, iron, and powdered silver nitrate is blended with combustible substance (citric acid) to form nanoparticles in an aqueous media. As an aliphatic tricarboxylic acid, citric acid serves as both a fuel and a solvent. On the heating mantle, the reactant precursor was heated to 100°C for one hour. After constant agitation and heat treatment, a glossy semi-solid gel was produced. Gel was heated up even further for two hours, from 110 to 130°C hot oven. It has been found that amorphous, glossy ceramic powder with uniform size can be manufactured. There were no lumps or agglomerations in the metal powder. FTIR, TGA, XRD, XRF, and SEM are used to characterize ceramic powder. The FTIR spectra showed the absence of any additional organic functional groups. Thermogravimetric analysis carried out using TGA. Heat is applied to ceramic powder at a rate of 10 degrees Celsius per minute, ranging from 30°C to 500°C. It has been demonstrated that nanoceramic powder is thermodynamically stable up to 312°C due to its weight retention rate of 76%. XRD revealed two theta values and peak intensities. The XRD pattern revealed that the nanoceramic powder was amorphous. According to an XRF research, the mass proportion of each component in the nanoceramic powder composition is displayed. FeO, Ag₂O, and Cu₂O have percentage masses of 74.5, 25.1, and 0.425, respectively. Measurement of the nanoceramic oxide material's particle size is done using a scanning electron microscope. The range of the nanoceramic particle's particle

size was 200–1000nm.Engine oil which acts as a plasticizer now has these particles added to enhance its biocompatibility and antidamaging qualities.

Keywords: Metal nitrates, Citric acid, water, heating mantle.

Introduction: Barium strontium and titanium nanoceramics prepared by sol-gel combustion method .Lemon juice used as a fuel in that process or it was acted as a burning agent. Microstructure, ferroelectric, dielectric and electrical properties of ceramics were enhanced.BaTiO₃nanoceramics was modified in terms of specific ferroelectric, dielectric, and electrical properties by substituting Sr²⁺. By substituting Sr²⁺, electrical and dielectric properties are improved. The electrical and dielectric characteristics have improved overall as a result of the Sr²⁺ substitution. However, there was a weakening of the ferroelectric properties, which is mostly related to a significant change in the solid's microstructure [1]. A novel sol-gel auto combustion method has been used to successfully synthesis the Fe₂O₃/CuFe₂O₄/chitosan nano composites. Iron (II) oxide and copper ferrite (CuFe₂O₄) were used to create the nanocomposites (Fe₂O₃) For the first time, onion was used as a green reductant to create nanostructures, which were then analysed by SEM, IR, VSM, TEM, and XRD. After that, chitosan was added to the water-dispersed nanostructures. Chitosan was employed [2].Nano particles of zinc oxide prepared by combustion method. Microscopy and spectroscopic methods, including X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform-Infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, UV-visible spectroscopy, and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM), were used to analyse the produced materials. To determine which of the two synthesised materials would work best as a chemiresistor, the sensing features of the two materials were compared and their liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) sensing properties were evaluated [3].Allium cepa bulb extract was said to be a cost-effective, ecologically friendly approach for producing nickel oxide nanoparticles that has a higher dielectric constant. With different concentrations of nickel oxide nanoparticles, the dielectric properties were investigated using an LCR metre. It was discovered that the dielectric constant decreases as the frequency increases, and a large dielectric constant of about 1275 has been achieved for NiO-40 with a minimum dielectric loss of 1.24 at 1 MHz [4].Lemon juice involved in the combustion method and by using this solvent MgFe₂O₄and Fluorescent nanoparticles (MgFNPs) were prepared.At various temperatures, annealing was applied to the

produced MgFNPs. Several approaches have been used to examine the structural, morphological, and biological properties of the synthesised and annealed MgFNPs. To evaluate the crystallite nature, shape, and particle size of MgFNPs, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were employed [5]. Zinc nitrate was used as a precursor, aluminium nitrate, magnesium, and terminaliacatappa seed extract was used as dopants, and zinc oxide was produced as the fuel. On the microstructural, optical, and electrical properties of ZnO nanoparticles, the effect of doping (Al, Al⁺Mn) was examined. The hexagonal wurtzite structure of the green produced doped and undoped ZnO nanoparticles shows a high degree of crystallinity. With an increase in mean grain size for Al doped ZnO nanoparticles, synthesised ZnO nanoparticles has a porous structure [6]. Using the citrate gel combustion method, ZnO, single-doped (Co-ZnO, Cu-ZnO), and co-doped ZnO ((Co, Cu)/ZnO) were successfully produced. The samples were examined using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), UV-visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-vis-DRS), Fourier transforms infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), and photoluminescence spectroscopy (PL). XRD patterns for (Co, Cu)/ZnO were used to calculate the average particle size, which was 30.33 nm. With Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, and Gram-positive *Aspergillus flavus* and *Candida albicans*, the antibacterial and antifungal properties of ZnO, Co-ZnO, Cu-ZnO, and (Co, Cu)/ZnO were investigated, respectively (fungal strain). The antibacterial activity was improved by the (Co, Cu)/ZnO [7]. The creation of silver nanoparticles has drawn increased interest because of its potential applications in a number of industries, including energy, electronics, medicine, and the environment. This particular work was focused on the synthesis of silver nanoparticles in bulk scale, free of capping agents, due to its very good catalytic activity. The environmentally friendly sol-gel auto combustion approach does away with risky reducing chemicals and time-consuming purifying procedures. By performing the basic reactions of nitrophenol reduction and methylene blue degradation, the silver nanoparticle's potential as a catalyst for the reduction of organic compounds and dye degradation was established [8]. Silver oxide nanoparticles made greenly for biomedical and photocatalytic environmental remediation [9]. XRD, SEM, and FTIR were used to characterise the produced zinc oxide nanoparticles. The average particle size computed as in the range of 25–50 nm by applying the

Scherer formula is seen in the XRD patterns of ZnO nanoparticles synthesized with the green synthesis approach utilising leaf extracts of adhatoda (adulsa), lemongrass, neem, meethi, and tulsi. Particle sizes between 85 and 100 nm are shown in the SEM image to have an uneven shape. Additionally, the 3,4-Dihydropyrimidinones from ethylacetoacetate, benzaldehyde, and urea were prepared using the synthesised ZnO catalyst in the Biginelli reaction with a product yield of about 75%**[10]**. The use of nanoparticles in the hydrocarbon sector serves a variety of functions that increase the amount of oil and gas produced. In petroleum applications, nanomaterials are employed as nanoparticles, nanosensors, nanocomposites, coated nanoparticles, nanofluids, etc. Therefore, the use of nanotechnology in the enhanced oil recovery (EOR) process aids in the extraction of trapped oil that is present below the surface. Eco-friendly and cost-effective nano ultrafine particles are available. A favourable environment for oil recovery is produced by the interaction of the injected fluid with the rock/oil system. The main objective of this work is to review the many kinds of nanoparticles and nanomaterials used in petroleum applications**[11]**.

- **Effect of used oil in engine:**

Several important advantages of using engine oil for your car are as follows:

1) Lubrication: By lowering friction between moving elements, engine oil protects vital components from deterioration. This lubricant is necessary to ensure the engine runs smoothly.

2) Heat Dissipation: The heat produced during combustion is partially dissipated by engine oil. The engine is kept at ideal operating temperatures by effective heat dissipation, which keeps it from overheating.

3) Removal of Contaminants: Additives in engine oil dissolve and clean up pollutants. It contributes to keeping an engine cleaner and more effective by preventing the accumulation of sludge, debris, and metal particles.

4) Seal Conditioning: Oil helps ensure that gaskets and seals inside the engine are operating correctly. It keeps them flexible, stopping leaks and guaranteeing a tight seal between parts.

5) Preventing Rust and Corrosion: Motor oil creates a barrier to guard metal surfaces from rust and corrosion. This is especially critical for preserving the longevity of engine components.

6) Engine Cleanliness: By shielding internal engine components from deposit accumulation, the detergents in engine oil maintain engine cleanliness. For the engine to run smoothly and last a long time, it must be clean.

7) Higher Fuel Economy: Engines with proper lubrication run with less friction, which increases fuel economy. Reduced fuel usage and improved overall performance are two benefits of smoothly running components.

8) Improved Engine Life: By minimizing wear, lowering friction, and maintaining the general health of your engine's components, regular use of high-quality oil.

The act of recycling deteriorated engine oil might result in a number of problems.

1. Oil loses its lubricating qualities, becomes contaminated, and experiences thermal breakdown over time. Reusing such deteriorated oil could lead to inadequate lubrication, elevated friction, and quicker engine component wear.

2. Old oil may also be less effective at dissipating heat, which raises operating temperatures and increases the risk of damage.

Reusing deteriorated engine oil can harm your engine for a number of reasons:

- **Loss of viscosity:** Over time, engine oil experiences heat breakdown and loses viscosity. For the right lubrication, this viscosity is essential. Reusing the oil may result in insufficient lubrication, which may cause engine parts to wear down and experience more friction.

- **Contamination Buildup:** Dirt, sludge, and metal fragments are among the pollutants that are accumulated by used oil. The oil's capacity to lubricate properly may be further hampered by these contaminants. Vital components may suffer damage and wear faster if these impurities are reintroduced into the engine.

- **Decreased Additive Effectiveness:** Engine oils are enhanced in performance by the addition of detergents for cleaning and dispersants for managing pollutants. Recurring use reduces these compounds' efficiency.

- **Higher Operating Temperatures:** Degraded oil may have trouble effectively dispersing heat. As a consequence, the engine may operate at higher temperatures than usual, which could overheat and harm delicate parts.

- **Corrosion and Oxidation:** Oil can experience chemical transformations over time that result in the production of acidic byproducts and oxidation. Engine component corrosion may result from reusing oil that has more oxidative and acidic qualities.

In summary, reusing degraded engine oil compromises its lubricating properties, accelerates wear and tear, and introduces harmful contaminants, ultimately posing a risk to the overall health and performance of your engine. Regular oil changes are crucial to maintaining optimal engine function and longevity.

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Damages of engine parts due to application of traditional engine oil .(viscosity increased as a result flowability decreases that effect the lubrication characteristics) as shown below

Piston ring affection

Dip stick (determines oil level)

High smoke

Damage the ring of piston

Methodology: a.

I. Development of liquid precursor of metallic salt:

A suitable amount of copper nitrate salt, iron salt, and silver salt were combined with aqueous medium in this step. Nitrate salt is an oxidant and the solvent citric acid served as a fuel. By supplying the oxygen needed for fuel combustion, nitrates satisfy the oxidant requirement. fuel uphold the consistency of the components' composition. At between 70 and 110 °C, thermal dehydration transformed the translucent aqueous solution containing a mixture of copper, iron, and silver salts into a thick liquid. Some of the key process parameters are the type of fuel, its quantity, and the pH of the starting solution in order to make translucent viscous gel without any phase separation or precipitation. A gel precursor was created by heating the mantle continuously.

II. Combustion of precursor

At a temperature of 150–250 °C, the precursor is heated to its melting point, which is when the combustion reaction begins exothermic in nature, the reaction involved the breakdown of the fuel-oxidant precursor along with the evolution of gasses and the creation of ceramic powder.

Flow diagram:

Image:

Prepared amorphous ceramic powder was incorporated in castor oil which acts as plasticizers. TAN number, Saponification number, viscosity flash point tests performed and observations were as follows.

1. Total acid number:

Temperature	Acid value of plasticizer	Acid value of ceramic + plasticizer	Temp. 300C	Acid value of plasticizer	Acid value of ceramic + plasticizer
30	0.38	0.22	1 sthr	0.39	0.22
40	0.38	0.21	2 ndhr	0.38	0.21
50	0.38	0.22	3rd hr	0.38	0.22
60	0.37	0.21	4th hr	0.38	0.22
70	0.38	0.22	6th hr	0.38	0.22
80	0.39	0.20	7th hr	0.39	0.21
90	0.37	0.21	8th hr	0.39	0.21

2.Saponification number:

Temp. ^o C	Saponificati on value of bio plasticizer	Saponification value of ceramic + bio plasticizer	Temp.30 OC	Saponificatio n value of bio plasticizer	Saponificatio n value of ceramic + bio plasticizer
30	176.5	95.5	1 sthr	177.5	95.5
40	176.8	96.5	2 ndhr	176..8	96.5
50	177.4	95.5	3rd hr	177.4	95.5
60	177.6	96.5	4th hr	176.6	96.5
70	177.6	95.6	6th hr	177.6	95.6
80	177.8	96.5	7th hr	177.8	95.5
90	175.5	96.5	8th hr	177.5	96.5

3.Viscosity:

Temp in oC	Viscosity of bio plasticizer	Viscosity of bio plasticizer	
		ceramic with plasticizer (blend -1)	Ceramic with plasticizer (blend -2)
30	1451	1454	1454
40	1254	1255	1255
50	874	876	876
60	484	483	483
70	372	382	382
80	339	341	341
90	79	82	82

4. Flash point:

Sr.no.	Flash point of plasticizers (°C)	Flash point of plasticizer+ metallic filler (°C)	Stability	Ageing Flash point of plasticizer	Flash point of plasticizer+ metallic filler (°C)
1	229	235	First hr	229	235
2	229	235	Second hr.	229	235
3	230	235	Third hr	230	235
4	230	235	Fourth hr.	230	235
5	230	235	Fifth hr	230	235
6	230	236	Sixth hr.	230	236
7	230	236	Seventh hr.	230	236

5.Results and discussion:

The viscosity value of the plasticizer has been found to remain unchanged when ceramic is added. With the addition of ceramic powder, the plasticizer's acid number and saponification number are greatly reduced. When ceramic powder is added, the plasticizer's flash point rises

- The product of the combustion process was pure, fine powders of oxide of copper, iron, and calcium that were formed at a lower calcination temperature.
- The powder was homogeneous, amorphous, and composed of very fine particles.
- One benefit of the combustion technique is the product's stable surface and high surface area.
- The acid value of the plasticizer containing ceramic was 55% lower than that of the plasticizer alone.
- The plasticizer's saponification value dropped by 54% when combined with ceramic.
- The addition of ceramic powder raised the plasticizer's flash point by 2%.
- A declining acid value means that plasticizer is not lost at high temperatures.
- A lower acid value indicates that the bio-plasticizer has little oxidation and can be used as a lubricant.
- At high temperatures, the loss of plasticizer is reduced.

Characterizations:

TGA:

Filename: C:\Users\TGA\Des...\CERAMIC of Fe+CU+AG.t6d
Operator ID:
Sample ID: ceramic of Fe+Cu+Ag
Sample Weight: 8.042 mg
Comment:

1) Heat from 30.00°C to 500.00°C at 10.00°C/min

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XRD:

No.	2-theta(deg)	ESD	d(ang.)	ESD	Height(counts)	ESD	FWHM(deg)	ESD	Int. I(counts deg)	ESD
67	32.5735	0.047026	2.74669	0.003852	136.33	11.6762	0.5026	0.069426	135.86	8.13511
68	35.5003	0.005175	2.52667	0.000356	2018.55	44.9283	0.3136	0.004849	861.14	8.51348
69	36.9487	0.047437	2.43088	0.003008	142.12	11.9213	0.9094	0.063731	175.76	9.56587
70	38.6954	0.006415	2.32507	0.000371	1834.66	42.833	0.4099	0.005806	1024.65	8.86102
71	48.7929	0.019456	1.86491	0.000698	486.91	22.066	0.3314	0.017643	219.82	5.52774
72	53.5529	0.023677	1.70983	0.0007	128.38	11.3306	0.4044	0.032896	64.53	3.8776
73	58.2466	0.036182	1.58272	0.000896	166.63	12.9084	0.4636	0.028281	88.3	5.00415
74	61.5565	0.020472	1.50532	0.000451	314.76	17.7414	0.3739	0.014825	131.35	4.61744
75	65.9054	0.024092	1.41613	0.000459	288.53	16.9862	0.7849	0.052017	309.75	19.6209
76	66.2934	0.011839	1.40878	0.000223	305.17	17.4692	0.2266	0.026194	104.71	14.2682
77	68.1404	0.013469	1.37502	0.000239	269.41	16.4139	0.5544	0.018912	185.89	6.22999
78	72.3136	0.039557	1.30559	0.000616	98.74	9.93672	0.4194	0.056072	62.03	4.37101
79	75.0051	0.0574	1.26528	0.000825	124.03	11.1369	0.6173	0.053632	93.42	5.50783

Int. W(deg)	ESD	Asym. factor	ESD	eta L/mL	ESD	eta H/mH	ESD	Size(ang.)	ESD
0.9965	0.145017	4.9994	3.82954	1.5438	0.160751	0.5655	0.928458	171.98	23.756
0.4266	0.013713	0.8002	0.05509	0.8751	0.046985	0.4867	0.035639	277.82	4.29534
1.2367	0.171051	0.7931	0.175601	0.8751	0.046985	0.4867	0.035639	96.2	6.74134
0.5585	0.017869	0.8305	0.055219	0.8751	0.046985	0.4867	0.035639	214.53	3.0385
0.4515	0.031813	0.9884	0.247127	0.3003	0.161027	0.9633	0.180622	274.91	14.6356
0.5026	0.074564	3.1157	0.965123	0.2091	0.23765	0.9841	0.396849	229.82	18.6941
0.5299	0.071086	1.4887	0.504641	0.0002	0.27648	0.4819	0.33917	204.89	12.4993
0.4173	0.038192	0.897	0.193211	0.288	0.189213	0.0003	0.184371	258.27	10.2394
1.0735	0.131204	1.8328	0.431281	0.0835	0.08532	1.3359	0.150527	125.98	8.34841
0.3431	0.066395	0.847	0.235333	0.0835	0.08532	1.3359	0.150527	437.24	50.5338
0.69	0.06516	4.1454	0.718059	0.0835	0.08532	1.3359	0.150527	180.69	6.16407
0.6282	0.107488	0.8702	0.342299	1.2868	0.461976	0.3913	0.44548	245.01	32.7527
0.7532	0.112042	0.529	0.256648	0.9218	0.449451	0	0.285879	169.42	14.7191

XRF:

Analyzed result

Sample Information

Sample name	CERAMICS CU+FE+AG
File name	CERAMICS CU+FE+AG
Application	Powders-FP
Date	08-04-2022 12:15
Analyzed by	MUKESH
Counts	1
Comment	Powder-FP

Meas. cond.

Diaphragm	DE-10mm	Atmosphere	Helium	Sample spin	None	Meas. order optimization	Yes
Condition name	Primary filter	Tube voltage(kV)	60.0	Tube current(µA)	200	ST(µsec)	50
High-Z_F	F	35.0	267	1.6	50	39.1	6.2
Mid-Z	C	6.5	455	1.6	50	37.4	
Low-Z	Open						

Analyzed result(FP method)

No.	Component	Result	Unit	Stat. Err.	LLD	LLQ
1	FeO	74.5	mass%			
2	Ag2O	25.1	mass%	0.0069	0.0132	0.0395
3	CaO	0.425	mass%	0.0014	0.0017	0.0050

Spectrum

SEM:

Conclusion:

- The following factors might produce low oil viscosity: heat cracking, viscosity shear down, coolant ingress, mixed lubricant, contaminants in the lubricant (non-lubricant mixing), etc. mentioned,
 - Excessive oil thickening can be caused by coolant leaks, oxidation, sludge and varnish formation, soot and carbon buildup, emulsification in oil, and moisture contamination.
 - Fine powders of metal nitrate of iron, copper, and silver ceramics were produced at lower calcinations temperatures efficiently with high surface area and stable product when ceramic additives (iron, copper, and silver) were synthesized using the sol-gel method instead of the conventional metal alkoxide,
 - Erosion of oil due to heavy metal might be lowered due to incorporation of ceramic in oil,
 - Oil consumption rate may be lower due to addition of ceramic in it,
 - High smoke resulted in to damage of ring piston can minimized due to ceramic incorporation of oil,
 - This study analyzes common key machinery component failures during regular usage, such as connecting rod, crankshaft, valve, piston, piston rings, etc., utilizing data from oil evaluation,
 - To analyze problems connected to oil thickening, low viscosity analysis, , diagnostic procedures, etc., elements collected from oil analysis and related information are used, utilizing the practical knowledge up to this point,
 - Later on, new ceramic additives created using the sol-gel process are described in detail, and first findings with and without additions together with utilized castor oil are shown,
 - Acid value of oil was reduced due to incorporation of ceramic in oil,
 - Saponification value of oil was reduced due to incorporation of ceramic in oil,
 - Viscosity of oil does not alter significantly due to ceramic addition,
 - Flash point of oil was increased due to incorporation of ceramic in oil
 - SEM indicates size of particle is in between 100 nm to 1000 nm
 - XRD shows amorphous nature of ceramic powder.
 - XRF indicates percentage of FeO= 74.5% ,Ag₂O=25.1%, CaO=0.425%
 - TGA graph shows that prepared ceramic powder is stable up to 350°C.

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